

Bloodwise

Data management plan required?	Encouraged. Website states 'Bloodwise expects valuable data, reagents and software arising from Bloodwise-funded research to be made available to the scientific community with as few restrictions as possible so as to maximise the value of the research and for eventual patient and public benefit. Such data must be shared in a timely and responsible manner, making use of online open repositories, public databases and community-led reagent stores.'
RDM policy Link	No link
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	research@bloodwise.org.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Bloodwise guidance for applicants

https://bloodwise.org.uk/sites/default/files/project_grants_-_guidance_for_applicants_-_june_2018.pdf

Accessed: June 2018